

UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB

Faculty of Electrical
Engineering and
Computing

*Our mission is to be an Institution of **high academic values** and **ethical principles**, a site of critical thinking and questioning, **a place of equality** for all its members and **a driving force** in the Croatian society.*

Gender Equality Status Analysis

An extensive assessment of **gender bias** and **inequalities** both inside the Institution and in the external Innovation Ecosystem where it is positioned.

This research has been carried out by FER in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The internal assessment followed the **three ERA priorities on Gender Equality*** and examined them in the context of **specific activity/service areas** inside FER through the collection of qualitative and quantitative data.

The data collection was conducted by the institution researchers, through **desk research, policy analysis, interviews, surveys and focus groups.**

Key Findings

HUMAN RESOURCES

FER follows the national regulations **for recruitment and hiring processes.** The Institution has a balanced gender success rate in applications for positions of teaching and research assistants, however **males are more successful in obtaining postdoc positions.**

Success rate of male and female applicants to positions in the last 5 years.

Teaching and research assistants

Postdocs

Academic positions

[*Council of the European Union \(2015\). Conclusions on advancing Gender Equality in the European Research Area. RECH 295, COMPET 551, SOC 703](#)

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It has been argued that maternity leave is causing **delays in the career progression** due to lower publication rates by female researchers. Regarding career trajectories, women leave in an early stage, as doctoral students or postdocs.

Work-life balance is also affected in administrative offices where all employees are women, as frequent parental and sick leaves have been reported to cause work overload. There have been difficulties in getting substitutes for maternity leave of research associates or project leaders for projects financed by the Croatian Science Foundation.

INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE

The majority of managerial positions is covered by men and decision-making bodies are imbalanced.

Faculty Council

79% Male Members

21% Female Members

Committees

78% Male Members

78% Male Members

22% Female Members

There are only few women in leading positions in the Institution's Departments.

Head of Department

Head of Administrative Unit

Head of Committee

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The Faculty has a long-term unofficial commitment to inclusion of women in management at all levels, but intends to institutionalise a **Gender Equality Plan**.

RESEARCH & TEACHING

There are **no official guidelines** on integrating gender analysis into research, since the Institution provides practical support to researchers, without intervening in research content.

Share of female researchers
among Principal Investigators
in the last 3 years

All Institutional Projects

11.7%

European Projects

10%

The Institution doesn't have any guidelines in place to **integrate a gender dimension into research content**; and no mechanism is set to ensure **gender sensitive teaching and curricula**.

STUDENT SERVICES

The main role of the Student Advisory Office is helping students with the motivation and learning difficulties and **does not apply a gender sensitive approach**. Overall, male students are the majority in all levels of STEM studies.

Postgraduate Level: 78% Male - 22% Female

Graduate Level: 80 % Male - 20% Female

Undergraduate Level: 77% Male - 23% Female

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Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

TRANSFER TO MARKET

The Institution shows a quite **balanced ratio between female and male researchers** participating in Croatian Science Foundation Projects.

According to the data from Croatian Scientific Bibliography, the **gender ratio between co-authors** of conference publications attributed to FER is relatively proportional.

However, women represent only **4% of patenting researchers**, while no female researchers have been identified in the teams of faculty spin offs.

INTERSECTIONALITY

The Institution implements an **Anti-discrimination Act and Ethics Code of the University of Zagreb**. Also, a **Person of Confidence** is elected by the Dean to whom employees can report any discrimination.

FER has an **Ethics Committee** responsible for the above Code of Ethics. This body deals with **discrimination, harassment and plagiarism** issues for all academic staff and students.

Students can also report to the Institution's **Student Ombudsperson** regarding issues of academic relations and student rights and freedoms.

However, it has been documented that the topic of intersectionality is **not well-known, thus raising awareness is highly recommended** for the academic community.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

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Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

The first part of the external assessment included an analysis of the **national legal and policy framework**. The second, focused on the **National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems**. A **context analysis** was implemented through a dedicated desk research and complemented with interviews with internal stakeholders. In addition to the context analysis, a **mapping** was conducted by FER to identify existing and potential synergies with external stakeholders. The mapping comprised a focus group with internal stakeholders; a survey for external stakeholders and a Social Network Analysis.

Key Findings

NATIONAL LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK

The **Article 14** of the **national Act on Gender Equality** states that **Research Performing Organisations are obliged to work on gender balance**, but they have the freedom to define and monitor their own gender equality policies.

Notable adopted policies include measures targeting political and decision-making processes, which prescribe **the quota of 40% of the underrepresented gender in local, regional and national bodies**, and measures regarding parental leaves, part-time contracts and breastfeeding breaks are foreseen in the national legislation. However, the **availability of childcare facilities is not homogeneously spread** through the country.

Gender equality and **gender mainstreaming** in research were set as one of the priorities by the **ERA Implementation Plan for Croatia 2016 - 2020**.

A new strategy on Gender Equality is expected for the period **2020 – 2024** which will describe specific measures for supporting and funding scientific research on gender issues.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

There is **great discrepancy** between the number of male and female STEM students both at high schools and higher education.

STEM High School Students
(1st gr., 2018/2019)

90% Male

10% Female

STEM Higher Education Students
(1st year, 2018/2019)

63,2% Male

36,8% Female

The evolution of the employment rate in Research and Innovation shows a decrease in the employment of females from 2014 to 2018, while the findings on **patent registrations, founders and leaders of start-ups** show a **sensible gender gap**.

Also, there is a **low share** of Croatia's publications integrating a **sex or gender dimension** in their research. But there is a positive trend on the recent **improvement** of services to support **women entrepreneurship**.

SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

In the national ecosystem of Croatia, the Institution has a wide network of partners and collaborations in STEM, especially with industrial and technical institutes, related to education and research activities as well to project cooperation.

The Social Network Analysis included 160 external stakeholders.

A general lack of female students and employees is documented, especially at the top leading positions. This is due to biased perceptions of STEM jobs mainly by girls, **leading to a need for awareness raising actions** such as events, campaigns, and/or workshops **involving role models**.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

Nearly 25% of the collaborations of FER with external stakeholders have a **female leadership**, but notably, the vast majority of those are with Schools.

The Institution has one collaboration with the Affinity Group Women in Engineering (WiE) that specifically focuses on gender issues.

Only a few external stakeholders already implement some measures for contrasting gender inequalities. However, the stakeholders who participated in the Institution's research **have expressed willingness to cooperate on the matter**, through joint projects and research on the topic, the organization of workshops, training, and lectures aimed at raising awareness.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#).

This research has been conducted in the context of Horizon 2020 project, CALIPER.

The results will be used for the project's next implementation phases.

FER is one of the 9 Research Organisations across Europe which participates in CALIPER to develop a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** and engage the local Innovation Hubs to transfer the gained knowledge beyond academia.

Discover more about CALIPER

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